

INSTRUCTIONAL AND DISTRIBUTED LEADERSHIP IN THE CHANGING SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT IN PROMOTING ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

The study dealt with instructional and distributed leadership of school head in the changing school environment in promoting organizational effectiveness in elementary schools in Bay District. Specifically, the study attempted to identify the instructional leadership practices as perceived by the respondents as to: defining and communicating the school goals, monitoring and providing feedback on the teaching and learning process and promoting school-wide professional development. This also manifests distributed leadership practices as to school culture, shared responsibility; and leadership practices. The respondents of the study describe school environment as to: professional learning community and learning environment. The effectiveness of the organization as perceived by the respondents is describe as the: teacher's performance and student's performance. Furthermore, this also attempted to determine if there is a significant relationship between instructional leadership to school environment and organizational effectiveness and to find out if distributed leadership is significantly related to school environment and organizational effectiveness. Generally, most of the respondents perceived the instructional leadership practices of school head as "highly practiced and distributed leadership practices as "highly manifested". Likewise, respondents also perceived the school environment as to professional learning community and learning environment as "highly effective". Most of the respondents reveal organizational effectiveness in terms of teachers' performance as "outstanding and students' performance as "excellent". The hypothesis stating that the instructional leadership does not significantly related to the school environment and organizational effectiveness of the school was not supported by the findings of the study when the test correlation was made and therefore not sustained. Likewise, in the test correlation between distributed leadership show positive significant relationship to school environment and organizational effectiveness of the school therefore the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship in the above mentioned is not supported by evidence and therefore not sustained the findings of the study. This study found limitations that need to be addressed in future studies. The researcher therefore recommended that: The school head may create a collaborative opportunity for teachers to strengthen instructional practice by examining students' performance. The school head are also encouraged to develop development programs and in-service activities that will educate teachers on the instructional and distributed leadership perspectives. The school head may also use this study to examine instructional and distributed leadership approaches to maximize teachers and student's performance. For the future researcher, he/she may pursue parallel study with more respondents and consider exploring other aspect of the variables which are not included in the study. It may be done in order to continue to validate the relatedness of instructional and distributed leadership of school head to school environment in promoting organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Leadership, School Environment Organizational Effectiveness